

Original article

Factors associated with dental caries among school children in Bauchi local government area, Bauchi state, Nigeria: a cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Background: Dental caries remains a prevalent oral health challenge among school-aged children in resource-limited settings, yet its associated factors in northern Nigeria are underexplored. This study investigated the factors associated with dental caries among children aged 7-14 years in Bauchi Local Government Area (LGA), Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 600 school children in public primary and junior secondary schools in Bauchi LGA from June to October 2023. Dental caries was assessed using the Decayed, Missing, and Filled Teeth (DMFT) index by calibrated examiners (inter-examiner kappa = 0.84). Anthropometric measurements determined wasting (weight-for-height z-score <-2) and stunting (height-for-age z-score <-2). Socio-demographic characteristics, oral hygiene status, and dietary habits were collected using structured questionnaires. Multivariable logistic regression analysis was employed to identify factors independently associated with dental caries. **Results:** Factors independently associated with dental caries included female sex (AOR=10.707, 95%CI=2.452-46.745, p=0.002), frequency of between-meal snacking with refined sugar thrice or more daily (AOR=12.971, 95%CI=3.300-18.667, p=0.001), wasting/severe wasting (AOR=2.776, 95%CI=1.849-4.168, p<0.001), and thinness/severe thinness (AOR=2.615, 95%CI=1.638-4.174, p=0.001). Stunting/severe stunting was associated with a negative effect (AOR=0.527, 95% CI=0.325-0.790, p=0.002).

Conclusion: Female gender, frequent snacking, and undernutrition (wasting and thinness) are significantly associated with dental caries among school children in Bauchi LGA. These findings underscore the need for integrated school health programs addressing both nutritional rehabilitation and oral health promotion.

Keywords: Associated factors, Bauchi, Dental caries, Nigeria, School children.

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Introduction

Dental caries remains one of the most prevalent non-communicable diseases globally, affecting an estimated 2.5 billion people.¹⁻³ Its impact is particularly profound in children, where it constitutes a leading cause of pain, sleep and eating difficulties, school absenteeism, reduced concentration, and diminished quality of life.³⁻⁵ The World Health Organisation recognises dental caries as a major public health concern, with a disproportionate burden borne by low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).¹⁻⁶ In Nigeria, the 2011 National Oral Health Survey revealed a high prevalence of dental caries, with a substantial proportion of the disease burden remaining untreated among children.⁷⁻⁹ While the biological process of caries is universal, driven by the

interaction of cariogenic bacteria, fermentable carbohydrates, susceptible tooth surfaces, and time, its distribution is strongly influenced by socioeconomic, behavioural, and environmental factors.^{2,10}

Dental caries is a multifactorial disease best understood within a multilevel risk framework that encompasses biological, behavioural, environmental, and socioeconomic determinants.¹¹ At the biological level, factors include salivary composition and flow, enamel defects, plaque accumulation, and host immune response.¹² Behavioural determinants include oral hygiene practices, dietary habits (particularly sugar consumption frequency), and healthcare-seeking behaviours.¹³ Environmental factors include fluoride exposure through water, toothpaste, or professional applications, while socioeconomic determinants comprise parental education, occupation, income, and access to dental services.^{14,15} This multilevel framework recognises that these factors do not operate in isolation but interact across levels. For instance, low socioeconomic status may limit access to fluoridated toothpaste (environmental), influence dietary patterns toward cariogenic foods (behavioural), and increase the likelihood of enamel hypoplasia through malnutrition (biological). Understanding these interconnected determinants is essential for designing effective interventions.^{11,15} In Sub-Saharan Africa, these determinants often cluster to create high-risk environments, including limited access to fluoridated water and affordable oral healthcare, dietary transitions toward sugary snacks and drinks, inadequate oral hygiene practices, and low levels of parental health literacy.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ Bauchi Local Government Area (LGA) exemplifies a setting in which these broad risk factors are likely to be operational. The LGA, with its mix of urban and rural communities, faces typical public health challenges, including poverty, high population density, and strained healthcare infrastructure. Furthermore, cultural practices, local dietary staples, and water composition may present unique, context-specific influences on children's oral health.

A preliminary study in this population reported a dental caries prevalence of 45.8%.²⁰ However, understanding the specific factors associated with dental caries—categorized within the established multilevel framework—is essential for: (1) enabling evidence-based policy and programming for school-based oral health initiatives; (2) guiding efficient resource allocation toward the most impactful interventions; (3) empowering schools

and parents with knowledge about significant local risk factors; and (4) contributing to the national oral health database to facilitate monitoring of trends and evaluation of future interventions.

Existing national and state-level data on dental caries are often too broad to inform action at the LGA level, and there is a paucity of comprehensive studies within Bauchi LGA that simultaneously examine biological, behavioural, environmental, and socioeconomic factors associated with dental caries among school children. This study addresses this gap by providing a holistic analysis of these factors within an established conceptual framework.

The study aimed to investigate the prevalence and factors associated with dental caries among primary and junior secondary school children in Bauchi LGA, Nigeria.

Specific Objectives:

1. To assess the socio-demographic, dietary, oral hygiene, and dental service utilisation characteristics of participants.
2. To identify biological, behavioural, environmental, and socioeconomic factors associated with dental caries in the study population.
3. To propose evidence-based recommendations for the development of preventive oral health programs.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in selected primary and junior secondary schools in Bauchi LGA of Bauchi State, North-Eastern Nigeria. Bauchi State lies at latitude 10.314159°N and longitude 9.846282°E, with a projected 2022 population of 8,308,800.²¹ The State comprises 20 LGAs, with children aged 1-14 years constituting approximately 30% of the total population.²¹ Bauchi LGA, the State capital, covers 3,219 km² and had a projected population of 881,600 in 2022. It consists of twelve administrative wards. The indigenous population primarily engage in trading, farming, artisanal work, and civil service.

Study Design

A school-based cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted from June to October 2023.

Study Population

The study population comprised children aged 7-14 years attending public primary and junior secondary schools in Bauchi LGA.

Inclusion Criteria

All children aged 7-14 years residing in and attending public primary and junior secondary schools in Bauchi LGA who provided assent and

whose parents gave written informed consent were included.

Exclusion Criteria

Children were excluded if they had:

- Systemic illnesses such as Diabetes Mellitus, Sickle Cell Anaemia, or HIV (as determined from school records or child interview)
- Traumatic tooth loss, orthodontic brackets, tooth stains, or congenital tooth anomalies
- Lack of parental consent or child assent

Sample Size Determination

The minimum sample size was calculated using the Fisher formula for cross-sectional studies:²²

$$n = Z^2P(1-P)/d^2$$

Where:

- $Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence level)
- $P =$ Expected proportion (54.4% or 0.544, based on a previous study by Akaji in southern Nigeria)²³
- $d =$ Absolute precision (5% or 0.05)

$$n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.544(1-0.544) / (0.05)^2$$

$$n = 3.8416 \times 0.544 \times 0.456 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 3.8416 \times 0.248064 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 0.953 / 0.0025$$

$$n = 381$$

Allowing for a 10% non-response rate ($n = 381 + 38 = 419$), a total of 600 participants were recruited to enhance the study's statistical power.

Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed.

Stage 1 - Ward Selection: From all 12 wards in Bauchi LGA, four were randomly selected by simple balloting: Makama/Sarkin Baki, Majidadi B, Kangyare/Tirwun, and Bishi/Miri.

Stage 2 - School Selection: Using a list of schools from the Bauchi State Universal Basic Education Board (BASUBEB), 5% of the total 233 schools (12 schools) were selected. These were proportionally allocated to the four selected wards based on the number of schools in each ward.

Stage 3 - Selection of Study Participants: Within each school, participants were selected using proportionate allocation by class, with individual participants chosen via systematic random sampling.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Bauchi State Ministry of Health Ethics and Research Committee (Protocol number: NHREC/03/11/19B/2021/62). Written permission was secured from BASUBEB and each school. Written informed consent was obtained from parents/guardians, and verbal assent was obtained from children.

Quality Assurance and Calibration

Prior to the commencement of the study, the principal investigator underwent two weeks of training in dental examination and DMFT estimation at the Department of Dentistry, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi. Calibration exercises were conducted on 30 children (not included in the main study) against a gold standard (consultant maxillofacial surgeon). Inter-examiner reliability yielded a kappa statistic of 0.84, indicating excellent agreement. Intra-examiner reliability was assessed by re-examining 10% of participants after 48 hours (kappa = 0.89). Four research assistants were trained in anthropometric measurements and in administering questionnaires.

Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted among 60 participants (10% of the target) at Zannuwa Primary and Junior Secondary School (Makama A ward), not included in the main study, to familiarise participants with procedures and pretest instruments.

Data Collection

Following participant selection, parent/guardian information sheets and consent forms were distributed. Data was collected using a structured proforma capturing:

- **Socio-demographic factors:** Age, sex, religion, address, parental occupation, education, income (classified using Ogunlesi's classification)²⁴
- **Behavioural factors:** Dietary habits (snacking patterns, sugary item consumption), oral hygiene practices (brushing methods, frequency, timing, fluoridated toothpaste use), post-snacking oral hygiene
- **Environmental factors:** Access to dental services, previous dental visits, reasons for visits
- **Biological factors:** Anthropometric status, dental caries status

Anthropometric Measurements

Weight was measured to the nearest 0.01 kg using a Seca® digital scale, calibrated before commencement and after every 10th participant. Height was measured using a stadiometer to the nearest 0.1 cm. BMI was calculated as weight (kg)/height (m²) and interpreted using WHO growth charts: underweight (<5th percentile), normal (5th to <85th percentile), overweight (85th to <95th percentile), obese (≥95th percentile).²⁵

Dental Examination

Examinations were conducted in school staff rooms with participants seated on chairs, using a

headlamp, disposable mouth mirrors, dental probes, and personal protective equipment. Oral hygiene status was assessed, and teeth were examined for decay (D/d), missing (M/m), and filled (F/f) teeth for both dentitions. DMFT/dmft indices were calculated. Caries prevalence was defined as DMFT/dmft ≥ 1 .

Follow-up

Feedback letters informed parents about their child's dental status. Parents of children with untreated caries were encouraged to attend the ATBUTH Dentistry Department. All participants received toothbrushes and brushing instructions.

Data Analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS version 24.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were summarised using means and standard deviations. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

The chi-square test assessed associations between categorical variables (dental caries presence and socio-demographic, behavioural, environmental, and biological factors). Variables with $p < 0.05$ in bivariate analysis were entered into multivariable logistic regression to identify independent associations. Adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Sociodemographic Characteristics

A total of 600 schoolchildren participated. The majority were females (54.3%), attended public schools (85.7%), and were aged 7-10 years (48.7%). Most mothers were full-time housewives (65.3%) with primary education (44.5%), while most fathers were civil servants (63.7%) with secondary education (44.3%) (Table 1).

logistic regression was used to determine the relationship. A confidence interval of 95% and a p-value of ≤ 0.05 were considered significant.

Oral Hygiene Practices (Behavioural Factors)

Most participants used fluoride toothpaste (94.5%) and employed the horizontal scrub technique (71.8%). Nearly half brushed once daily (48.8%), primarily in the morning (56.7%). The majority (84.0%) did not use dental floss, primarily due to lack of awareness (82.3%) (Table 2).

management by dental consultation (35.8%), over-the-counter medication (33.6%), or traditional remedies (19.4%). Approximately one-fifth (18.8%) had a history of tooth extraction, primarily due to dental caries (54.2%) (Table 3).

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants (N=600)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Age group (years)		
7-8	103	17.2
9-10	189	31.5
11-12	143	23.8
13-14	165	27.5
Mean \pm SD	10.70 \pm 2.1	
Sex		
Male	274	45.7
Female	326	54.3
Social class		
Lower	216	36.0
Middle	320	53.3
Upper	64	10.7
Father's education		
None	8	1.3
Primary	98	16.3
Secondary	266	44.3
Tertiary	228	38.0
Mother's education		
Primary	267	44.5
Secondary	227	37.8
Tertiary	106	17.7
Mother's occupation		
Housewife	392	65.3
Business	204	34.0
Civil servant	4	0.7
Father's occupation		
Public servant	381	63.7
Business	172	28.7
Private company	46	7.7

Oral Health-Seeking Behaviour (Environmental Factors)

Most participants (77.5%) had never visited a dentist. Among those who had visited ($n=135$, 22.5%), most (62.2%) had their first visit after age five, and 51.1% visited only when necessary. Over half (55.0%) had experienced a toothache, with

Table 2: Oral Hygiene Practices Among Participants (N=600)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Tooth cleaning aids used		
Fluoride toothpaste/brush	567	94.5
Charcoal	25	4.2
Chewing stick	8	1.3
Method of cleaning		
Horizontal scrub	431	71.8
Vertical scrub	77	12.8
Circular motions	92	15.3
Frequency of cleaning		
Once daily	293	48.8
Twice daily	253	42.2
Others	54	9.0
Time of cleaning		
Morning only	340	56.7
Other times	260	43.3
Use of dental floss		
Yes	96	16.0
No	504	84.0
Reason for non-use of floss (n=504)		
Lack of awareness	415	82.3
Not considered important	73	14.5
No access	16	3.2
Tooth cleaning aids used		
Fluoride toothpaste/brush	567	94.5
Charcoal	25	4.2
Chewing stick	8	1.3
Method of cleaning		
Horizontal scrub	431	71.8
Vertical scrub	77	12.8
Circular motions	92	15.3

Dietary Habits (Behavioural Factors)

Most participants (59.1%) snacked once daily between meals, with 25.7% snacking twice daily and 15.2% thrice or more. The majority consumed sweets/chocolate (93.3%), chewing gum (91.5%), soft drinks (90.5%), biscuits (95.3%), and cake (85.0%). Among those who snacked, only 41.3% brushed their teeth afterwards, while 70.8% rinsed their mouths (Table 4).

Anthropometric Characteristics (Biological Factors)

Based on weight-for-age, 63.8% had normal weight, 27.2% were underweight, 6.3% had wasting, and 2.7% had severe wasting. Height-for-age assessment showed 69.8% had normal height, 27.7% were stunted, and 2.5% were severely stunted. BMI-for-age indicated 75.9% had normal BMI, 7.0% were overweight, 0.5% were obese, 16.0% were thin, and 0.7% had severe thinness (Table 5).

Table 3: Oral Health-Seeking Behaviour of Participants

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Ever visited a dentist (N=600)		
Yes	135	22.5
No	465	77.5
Frequency of dental visits (n=135)		
Once a year	46	34.1
Twice a year	20	14.8
Only when necessary	69	51.1
Age at first dental visit (n=135)		
≤5 years	51	37.8
>5 years	84	62.2
Mean ± SD	6.59±2.7 yrs	
Ever experienced toothache (N=600)		
Yes	330	55.0
No	270	45.0
Management of toothache (n=330)		
Saw dentist	118	35.8
Saw doctor	27	8.2
Self-medication	111	33.6
Traditional remedy	64	19.4
Other	10	3.0
Ever had tooth extraction (N=600)		
Yes	113	18.8
No	487	81.2
Reason for extraction (n=133)*		
Dental caries	72	54.2
Broken tooth	29	21.8
Accident	18	13.5
Other	14	10.5

Table 4: Dietary Habits Among Participants (N=600)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Frequency of between-meal snacking with refined sugar		
Once daily	355	59.1
Twice daily	154	25.7
Thrice or more daily	91	15.2
Consume sweets/chocolate		
Yes	560	93.3
No	40	6.7
Consume soft drinks		
Yes	543	90.5
No	57	9.5
Consume biscuits		
Yes	572	95.3
No	28	4.7
Brush teeth after snacking		
Yes	248	41.3
No	352	58.7
Rinse mouth after snacking		
Yes	425	70.8
No	175	29.2

Table 5: Anthropometric Characteristics of Participants (N=600)

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Weight-for-age z-score		
Normal	383	63.8
Underweight	163	27.2
Wasting	38	6.3
Severe wasting	16	2.7
Height-for-age z-score		
Normal	419	69.8
Stunted	166	27.7
Severe stunting	15	2.5
BMI-for-age		
Normal	455	75.9
Overweight/Obese	45	7.5
Thin/Severe thinness	100	16.7

the decayed component contributing most substantially (mean DT = 0.74 ± 1.1) (Table 6).

Table 6: Dental Caries Status Among Participants (N=600)

Variable	n (%)	Mean ± SD
Prevalence of dental caries	275 (45.8)	
Decayed teeth		0.74 ± 1.1
0	375 (62.5)	
≥1	225 (37.5)	
Missing teeth (due to caries)		0.24 ± 0.7
0	526 (87.7)	
≥1	74 (12.3)	
Filled teeth		0.03 ± 0.3
0	592 (98.7)	
≥1	8(1.3)	

Dental Caries Status

Decayed teeth were observed in 36.9% of participants, missing teeth due to caries in 12.3%, and filled teeth in only 1.4%. The mean DMFT score was 1.15 ± 1.60, with

DMFT score

1.15 ± 1.60

Table 7: Bivariate Analysis of Factors Associated with Dental Caries

Variable	Caries Present (n=275) n (%)	Caries Absent (n=325) n (%)	χ ²	P-value
Age group yrs			58.08	<0.001
7-8	67 (65.0)	36 (35.0)		
9-10	113 (59.8)	76 (40.2)		
11-12	43 (30.1)	100 (69.9)		
13-14	52 (31.5)	113 (68.5)		
Sex			6.57	0.010
Male	110 (40.1)	164 (59.9)		
Female	165 (50.6)	161 (49.4)		
Father's education			15.36	0.002
None	8 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Primary	34 (34.7)	64 (65.3)		
Secondary	121 (45.5)	145 (54.5)		
Tertiary	112 (49.1)	116 (50.9)		
Mother's occupation			7.82	0.020
Housewife	193 (49.2)	199 (50.8)		
Business	82 (40.2)	122 (59.8)		
Civil servant	0 (0.0)	4 (100.0)		
Father's occupation			29.94	<0.001
Public servant	199 (52.1)	183 (47.9)		
Business	49 (28.5)	123 (71.5)		
Private company	27 (58.7)	19 (41.3)		
Weight-for-age			25.49	<0.001
Normal	150 (39.2)	233 (60.8)		
Underweight	102 (62.6)	61 (37.4)		
Wasting/Severe wasting	23 (42.6)	31 (57.4)		
Height-for-age			21.47	<0.001
Normal	218 (52.0)	201 (48.0)		
Stunted/Severe stunting	57 (31.5)	124 (68.5)		
BMI-for-age			13.47	0.004
Normal	197 (43.3)	258 (56.7)		
Overweight/Obese	17 (37.8)	28 (62.2)		
Thin/Severe thinness	61 (61.0)	39 (39.0)		

Factors Associated with Dental Caries (Bivariate Analysis)

Significant associations with dental caries were observed for age ($\chi^2=58.082$, $df=3$, $p<0.001$), female sex ($\chi^2=6.570$, $df=1$, $p=0.010$), father's education ($\chi^2=15.359$, $df=3$, $p=0.002$), mother's occupation ($\chi^2=7.823$, $df=2$, $p=0.020$), father's occupation ($\chi^2=29.940$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$), weight-for-age ($\chi^2=25.495$, $df=2$, $p<0.001$), height-for-age ($\chi^2=21.473$, $df=1$, $p<0.001$), and BMI-for-age ($\chi^2=13.469$, $df=3$, $p=0.004$) (Table 7).

Independent Factors Associated with Dental Caries (Multivariable Analysis)

Multivariable logistic regression analysis identified several factors independently associated with dental caries (Table 8). Female sex was associated with markedly increased odds of dental caries (AOR=10.707, 95%CI=2.452-46.745, $p=0.002$).

Frequency of between-meal snacking with refined sugar was strongly associated, with thrice or more daily snacking conferring approximately 13-fold increased odds compared to once daily (AOR=12.971, 95%CI=3.300-18.667, $p=0.001$).

Nutritional status emerged as a significant biological factor. Children with wasting or severe wasting had nearly threefold increased odds of dental caries (AOR=2.776, 95%CI=1.849-4.168, $p<0.001$), and those with thinness or severe thinness had similarly elevated odds (AOR=2.615, 95%CI=1.638-4.174, $p=0.001$). Stunting or severe stunting was associated with a negative effect (AOR=0.527, 95% CI=0.325-0.790, $p=0.002$). Age 13-14 years was associated with lower odds of caries compared to the 7-8 years reference group (AOR=0.011, 95%CI=0.001-0.182, $p=0.002$).

Table 8: Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Independently Associated with Dental Caries

Variable	Adjusted Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-value
Age group (years)			
7-8	1.000 (Reference)		
9-10	0.463	0.053-4.065	0.487
11-12	0.111	0.013-0.946	0.044
13-14	0.011	0.001-0.182	0.002
Sex			
Male	1.000 (Reference)		
Female	10.707	2.452-46.745	0.002
Frequency of between-meal snacking			
Once daily	1.000 (Reference)		
Twice daily	2.316	0.108-5.402	0.786
Thrice or more daily	12.971	3.300-18.667	0.001
Weight-for-age			
Normal	1.000 (Reference)		
Underweight	1.548	0.846-2.844	0.157
Wasting/Severe wasting	2.776	1.849-4.168	<0.001
Height-for-age			
Normal	1.000 (Reference)		
Stunted/Severe stunting	0.527	0.325-0.790	0.002
BMI-for-age			
Normal	1.000 (Reference)		
Overweight/Obese	1.112	0.589-2.108	0.745
Thin/Severe thinness	2.615	1.638-4.174	<0.001

Model adjusted for father's education, mother's occupation, father's occupation, method of cleaning teeth, time of cleaning, previous dental visit, consumption of chewing gum and cake, and post-snacking oral hygiene practice

Discussion

This study investigated factors associated with dental caries among school children in Bauchi LGA, identifying several independent associations, including female sex, frequent between-meal snacking, and undernutrition (wasting and thinness).

Sex as a Biological/Sociocultural Factor

Female sex emerged as a strong independent factor associated with dental caries, with girls having approximately 10-fold higher odds than boys. This finding aligns with studies from northern Appalachia, USA;²⁷ Rwanda;²⁸ Libya; and Ethiopia.³⁰ Within the multilevel caries framework, this disparity likely results from complex interactions between biological factors (genetics, hormonal influences, earlier tooth eruption in girls) and behavioural/sociocultural factors (culturally-determined dietary preferences, oral hygiene practices).³¹ The earlier eruption of permanent teeth in girls exposes teeth to cariogenic challenges for longer periods. Additionally, sociocultural norms may influence dietary patterns and healthcare-seeking behaviours differentially between sexes. Further research is warranted to elucidate the mechanisms underlying this gender disparity in our context.

Dietary Habits as Behavioural Factors

Frequent between-meal snacking with refined sugar was strongly associated with dental caries, with thrice-or-more daily snacking increasing the odds by approximately 13-fold compared to once daily. This dose-response relationship underscores the cumulative effect of repeated sugar exposure on caries development and is consistent with the well-established cariogenic mechanism: frequent sugar consumption provides substrate for acid production by cariogenic bacteria (*Streptococcus mutans* and *Lactobacillus* species), prolonging periods of low oral pH and promoting demineralisation.³² Our findings corroborate a Nepalese study in which daily consumption of sweets and processed snacks was associated with a 74% caries prevalence.³³ Similarly, a systematic review of longitudinal studies in children aged 6-12 years found that candy consumption (>once weekly), daily fruit juice intake, and bedtime soft drink consumption were strongly linked to caries onset.³⁴ Notably, only 41.3% of our participants brushed their teeth after snacking, and 70.8% rinsed their mouths, suggesting missed opportunities for mitigating caries risk through post-prandial oral hygiene—a behavioural factor amenable to intervention.

Nutritional Status as a Biological Factor

The relationship between nutritional status and dental caries in our study was complex. Wasting/severe wasting and thinness/severe thinness were associated with significantly increased odds of dental caries, consistent with findings from other studies.³⁵⁻³⁷ This association may be explained through multiple biological pathways. Malnutrition-induced immunosuppression could facilitate the proliferation of cariogenic bacteria. Protein-energy malnutrition affects salivary gland structure and function, reducing salivary flow and compromising its protective properties—including buffering capacity, antimicrobial activity, and remineralisation potential.³⁸ Furthermore, undernourished children may have enamel hypoplasia, creating retentive sites that predispose to caries.³⁹ These biological mechanisms operate within the broader context of socioeconomic disadvantage that often accompanies malnutrition. Stunting was negatively associated with dental caries in our analysis—an unexpected finding that contrasts with several studies reporting positive associations between stunting and caries.^{40,41} However, a systematic review by Sadida et al. noted heterogeneity in the literature, with some studies showing no association or inverse relationships depending on population and caries measure used.⁴² Potential explanations within our context include: dietary patterns associated with stunting (perhaps lower consumption of cariogenic foods due to reduced appetite or household food insecurity patterns), delayed tooth eruption in stunted children, reducing the duration of caries exposure, or the complex bidirectional nature of the caries-malnutrition relationship, where caries-related pain may alter dietary intake and growth patterns. Longitudinal studies are needed to clarify these temporal relationships.

Dental Service Utilisation as an Environmental Factor

Our finding that 77.5% of children had never visited a dentist reflects significant environmental barriers to access to oral healthcare in this population, consistent with reports from other Nigerian studies.⁴³ Among those experiencing a toothache, only 35.8% consulted a dentist, with many resorting to self-medication or traditional remedies. This pattern of delayed professional care likely contributes to disease progression and the high proportion of missing teeth observed. The extremely low rate of filled teeth (1.4%) relative to decayed (36.9%) and missing (12.3%) teeth indicates a predominantly restorative care deficit, highlighting environmental barriers including limited

dental facilities, financial constraints, and low oral health literacy.

Socioeconomic Factors

While father's education, mother's occupation, and father's occupation showed significant bivariate associations, these did not remain significant in multivariable analysis, suggesting that their effects may be mediated through behavioural and biological pathways. This aligns with the multilevel framework, in which socioeconomic position influences distal determinants (access, knowledge) that shape proximal behavioural and biological risk factors.¹¹

Implications for Public Health Practice

Our findings have several implications for oral health policy and programming in Bauchi LGA and similar resource-limited settings, organised within the multilevel framework:

1. **Behavioural interventions:** School-based oral health education should address knowledge gaps regarding proper brushing techniques, the importance of twice-daily brushing with fluoride toothpaste, and the cariogenic potential of frequent snacking. Post-snacking oral hygiene should be emphasised.
2. **Biological/nutritional interventions:** The strong association between undernutrition and caries suggests that oral health and nutrition programs should be integrated. School feeding programs could promote nutritious, low-carbohydrate foods while delivering oral health messages.
3. **Targeted approaches for girls:** The striking gender disparity warrants further investigation and targeted interventions addressing girls' oral health needs, considering both biological and sociocultural factors.
4. **Environmental interventions:** Improving access to preventive and restorative care through school-based fluoride varnish programs, promoting affordable fluoridated toothpaste, and strengthening referral

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that dental caries is a significant public health problem among school children in Bauchi LGA. Female sex (biological/sociocultural factor), frequent between-meal snacking with refined sugar (behavioural factor), wasting, and thinness (biological factors) emerged as independent positive associations, while stunting showed a negative association. The findings highlight the complex interplay between biological, behavioural, environmental, and socioeconomic factors in determining oral health outcomes. The extremely low utilisation of dental services and the predominance of untreated decay underscore critical environmental barriers to access to oral healthcare.

pathways to dental services could address the current treatment gap.

Socioeconomic considerations: Community awareness campaigns should emphasise the importance of regular dental check-ups and early treatment seeking, with consideration of barriers faced by lower socioeconomic groups.

Strengths and Limitations

Strengths: This study employed a robust multistage sampling technique, achieved a large sample size (N=600), and utilised multivariable analysis to identify independent associations while controlling for potential confounders. The inclusion of anthropometric measurements allowed simultaneous examination of nutritional status and oral health, addressing an important gap in the literature. Calibrated examiners ($\kappa = 0.84$) and standardised protocols enhanced data quality. The conceptual framework guided a comprehensive assessment of biological, behavioural, environmental, and socioeconomic factors.

Limitations: The cross-sectional design precludes the establishment of causal relationships. The study was conducted in public schools, potentially limiting generalizability to private school attendees who may have different risk profiles. Reliance on self-reported dietary and oral hygiene practices may be subject to recall and social desirability biases. The exclusion of children with systemic illnesses, though methodologically sound, may have underestimated the caries burden in vulnerable populations. The unexpected negative association with stunting warrants cautious interpretation and further investigation through longitudinal designs. Plaque index and salivary studies were not conducted, limiting the assessment of certain biological factors.

These results call for urgent, multifaceted interventions, including school-based oral health education, integration of oral health promotion with nutrition programs, targeted approaches to address gender disparities, and improved access to preventive and restorative dental services. Longitudinal studies are needed to elucidate causal pathways, particularly the relationship between stunting and caries, and to evaluate the effectiveness of integrated interventions. By addressing these associated factors within a comprehensive framework, policymakers and health practitioners can work to reduce the burden of dental caries and improve the oral health and overall well-being of school children in Bauchi LGA and similar settings across Nigeria.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no financial or non-financial conflicts of interest associated with this study.

Authors' Contributions

Ahmed F. Saleh (Lead Investigator): Conceptualised the study, designed the methodology, supervised data collection, performed statistical analysis, and drafted the initial manuscript.

Garba Mohammed Ashir (Research Supervisor): Supervised all aspects of the research, critically revised the manuscript for intellectual content, and approved the final version.

Muhammad Bashir Faruk (Research Supervisor): Provided supervisory oversight, contributed to study design, and critically reviewed the manuscript.

Bashar Salisu Yaro (Research Assistant): Assisted with data collection and analysis, contributed to the literature review, and revised the manuscript.

Taiye Tony Izegaegbe (Oral and Maxillofacial Surgeon): Provided specialised training in dental examination techniques, conducted calibration exercises, contributed expertise on oral health systems, and critically revised the manuscript.

All authors approved the final version of the manuscript and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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